

HOW ORGANIZATIONAL TRUST AND ORGANIZATIONAL JUSTICE IMPACT ON ORGANIZATIONAL CITIZENSHIP BEHAVIOR (OCB)? : A STUDY IN A PUBLIC HOSPITAL

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Abstract

One approach to managing an organization to increase performance and the quality of its services is to implement the utilization of quality human resources that will help the organization carry out the desired service system. The success of an organization is not only determined by employee behavior that is determined according to their job description (in-role behavior), but also by employee behavior that is outside their job description (extra-role behavior). There have been many studies on OCB, but not many previous studies have raised organizational trust and organizational justice as influencing variables. Organizational trust and organizational justice both play an important role in organizational progress and are factors that affect OCB. This study aims to see the effect of organizational trust (OT) and organizational justice (OJ) on organizational citizenship behavior (OCB). This research is a quantitative study with a cross-sectional approach. The sample consisted of 255 employees of the Prof. DR. H. M. Anwar Makkatutu Hospital Bantaeng in South Sulawesi Province who were selected by *proportionate stratified random sampling* and then analyzed using the Logistic Regression Analysis on SPSS. The results showed that organizational trust (P-value 0.001 < 0.005, Exp(B) = 6.035, B 1.798) and organizational justice (P-value 0.001 < 0.005, Exp(B) = 53.205, B 3.974) had a significant positive effect on OCB. Based on the research results, it can be seen that organizational trust and organizational justice variables have a major influence on organizational citizenship behavior (OCB). So hospital management needs to pay attention to these two variables in the continuity of an organization, which will have an impact on improving hospital performance. In the future, research can be carried out by adding a more heterogeneous population from other hospitals, both government-owned and private hospitals, and there are other variables that can be associated with the two variables in this study related to OCB.

Keywords: Organizational Trust (OT), Organizational Justice (OJ), Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB).

INTRODUCTION

Implementing the use of quality human resources that will assist the organization in carrying out the expected service system is one alternative to managing an organization in order to improve performance and the quality of its services. According to Andrew 2015, employee willingness to contribute is a key factor in the organization's capacity to meet its objectives[1]. Employee behavior that the company expects of them and that the company demands is not limited to role behavior; it also includes extra role behavior known as organizational citizenship behavior (OCB).

Organizational citizenship behavior (OCB) is a personal conduct of autonomy that promotes efficient workplace operations but is not specifically acknowledged by the formal incentive structure of the business [2]; [3]; [4]. This OCB behavior is very important for organizations where sometimes formally stated job descriptions are not

enough to achieve the goals of the organization [5]. So there is a need for cooperative behavior that can help the organization function. OCB contributes to the achievement of organizational goals by facilitating the wise allocation of corporate financial and human resources [3].

OCB contributes positively to decreased turnover intention, increased employee satisfaction, and higher organizational performance. And as an extra-role behavior, OCB can serve to help new employees adjust to their positions as quickly as possible [6], helping teams solve complex problems [7]. Based on several literature reviews, there are four major categories of antecedent factors that affect OCB, according to Podsakoff, MacKenzie, et al. 2000, namely: individual characteristics, job characteristics, organizational attitudes, and leadership [8]. Some important variables identified as antecedents of OCB include: organizational commitment, job satisfaction, task clarity, organizational support, organizational justice, transformational leadership, and organizational trust [9]; [10].

Researchers use organizational trust and organizational justice variables in examining OCB because, currently, organizational trust and organizational justice both play an important role in organizational progress and are factors that influence OCB. Organizational studies academics and practitioners have also been interested in organizational justice and trust for the past ten years [11]. Various fields of study, including leadership, organizational change, organizational learning, conflict resolution, and so on, have emphasized the importance of trust. Many organizational outcomes, including work output, organizational commitment, organizational climate, team effectiveness, and organizational competitiveness, are significantly impacted by trust [12]. With the introduction of organizational transformation and management innovation in recent years, a loss of trust has emerged as one of the primary issues facing businesses. Because trust has a significant influence on performance outcomes and workplace behavior, it is a topic of interest [12]. Organizational trust (OT) itself is an employee's recognition and trust in the sincerity and reliability of the organization or leadership and their willingness to establish a long-term relationship with the organization. The relationship between organizational trust and OCB reflects a social exchange relationship. Trust creates a good working environment for the organization where employees show more out-of-role behaviors [13].

In addition, justice in the organization is vital and influential. Injustice produces unhappiness, which, if not addressed immediately, can lead to deviant behavior in the workplace [14]. When employees are treated fairly in the work environment, they tend to work well, help the organization, and display OCB. Organizational justice is an important concept and organizational practice in modern organizational management. Improving organizational justice has a direct and positive effect on improving the performance of personnel in the organization, the emergence of OCB behavior, increasing mental health, and various other positive attitudes that affect the sustainability of the organization. If individuals are treated fairly by the organization, members are more willing to show their OCB [15].

RSUD Prof. Dr. H. M. Anwar Makkatutu Bantaeng is a class B hospital owned by the local government and is the only referral center in Bantaeng Regency, South Sulawesi. Where the data on the achievement of national quality indicators in 2022 was obtained, the achievement rate on several indicators has not reached the standard. The indicators that have not reached the standard are the 73% hand hygiene compliance

indicator (standard: >85%) and the compliance of PPE use at 88.9% (standard: 100%). The achievement of these indicators illustrates that the performance of Prof. Dr. H. M. Anwar Makkatutu Bantaeng Hospital in 2022 is not optimal. So it is important to improve hospital performance through the organizational citizenship behavior of employees in the hospital. Employee behavior that is outside of their job description (extra-role behavior), such as the desire to use their work time wisely and the willingness to collaborate, support one another, offer suggestions, take an active role, and provide extra services, is just as important to an organization's success as behavior that is defined by their job description. With the low compliance with the achievement of this indicator, the researcher assumes that this is due to the low OCB behavior of employees.

This is also supported in the initial data collection on 20 employees at Prof. Dr. H. M. Anwar Makkatutu Bantaeng Hospital. It is known that for the aspect of conscientiousness, 12 people (60%) stated that they did not care when in the workplace there were employees who did not comply with the rules. In the aspect of altruism, 5 people (25%) stated that they would let their coworkers know when their coworkers were having trouble with their work because it was their responsibility. In the aspect of sportsmanship, six people (30%) stated that they did not care and continued to do their work when they saw their coworkers doing something that could harm the organization for their personal interests. In the aspect of courtesy, 5 people (25%) stated that they would be firm with the opinion they thought was right when they differed with other coworkers. Meanwhile, in the civic virtue aspect, 8 people (40%) stated that they felt burdened when there was a change in leadership in the organization.

Based on previous literature reviews, it is also stated that OCB is one of the effective variables to improve performance in Hospitals. Thus making researchers interested in examining factors that can increase employee OCB behavior at Prof. Dr. H. M. Anwar Makkatutu Bantaeng Hospital.

METHOD

Study Setting

This research is a quantitative study with a cross-sectional approach. This research was conducted in 2024 at the Prof. DR. H. M. Anwar Makkatutu Bantaeng in South Sulawesi Province. The population of this study was employees at the Prof. DR. H. M. Anwar Makkatutu Bantaeng in South Sulawesi Province, totaling 692 people, including doctors, dentists, nurses, midwives, pharmacists and pharmacist assistants, laboratory assistants, radiographers, nutritionists, physiotherapists, other health workers, management, and others. The sample size was calculated using the Slovin formula with a margin error of 5%, so a sample size of 255 employees was obtained. The sample count has reached the minimal number of samples required for quantitative research. The sampling technique was proportionate stratified random sampling, selected by inclusion and exclusion criteria.

Questionnaire and Data Analysis

In this study, questionnaires with a Likert scale and interviews were used as instruments. Organizational trust is measured using the Organizational Trust Inventory (OTI) questionnaire by Celep 2012, which consists of 36 items to measure organizational trust. OTI is classified into three dimensions: trust to work team, trust to

setting, and trust to management. Organizational justice is measured using a questionnaire, which includes 15 question items consisting of 3 dimensions, namely: distributive, procedural, and interactional. Organizational citizenship behavior is measured using a questionnaire, which includes 24 question items consisting of 5 dimensions, namely: altruism, conscientiousness, courtesy, civic virtue, and sportsmanship.

This instrument has been tested for construct validity and reliability using 30 respondents at Prof. DR. H. M. Anwar Makkatutu Hospital, Bantaeng. The reliability test results show that all question items in this research questionnaire are reliable, as seen from the Cronbach's alpha value of > 0.80. The validity test results show that all question items in the questionnaire are valid, as seen from the person correlation value > r table (0.361), which ranges from 0.362 to 0.873. Data analysis used the Logistic regression analysis test is an approach to creating a prediction model that is used to analyze the effect between the independent variable and the dependent variable (binary), which is dichotomous (2 categories, such as yes and no, high and low). using the SPSS application. In this study, the data analysis findings were given in tabular form along with a narrative-style explanation.

RESULTS

Table 1, shows the characteristics of respondents, including age, gender, education, and employment status. It shows that the respondents in this study were dominated by respondents aged 36–45 years, with as many as 101 people (39.6%). Based on gender, the respondents were dominated by women, with as many as 221 people (86.7%), while the remaining 34 were male (13.3%). The education level of the respondents was dominated by D3/equivalent for as many as 105 people (41.2%), and most of the respondents had honorer status for as many as 120 people (47.1%).

Table 1: Frequency distribution of respondent characteristics

No	Characteristics of Respondents	Amount		Total
		n	%	
1	Age (years)			
	20-35	95	37.3	255
	36–45	101	39.6	
	>45	59	23.1	
2	Gender			
	Male	34	13.3	255
	Female	221	86.7	
3	Education			
	D3/equivalent	105	41.2	255
	D4/S1/ equivalent	92	36.1	
	S2	24	9.4	
	Others	34	13.3	
4	Employment status			
	PNS	58	22.7	255
	Contract workers	55	21.6	
	Honorer	120	47.1	
	Others	22	8.6	

Source: Primary Data, 2024

Based on the output of Table 2, shows that of the 255 respondents at Prof. Dr. H. M. Anwar Makkatutu Bantaeng Hospital, there are 45.1% (115 respondents) with OCB in the high category and 54.9% (140 respondents) with OCB in the low category.

Table 2: Distribution of Respondents Based on Organizational Citizenship Behavior

OCB	n	(%)
High	115	45.1
Low	140	54.9
Total	255	100

Source: Primary Data, 2024

Based on the output of Table 3, shows that of the 255 respondents at Prof. Dr. H. M. Anwar Makkatutu Bantaeng Hospital, there are 34.5% (88 respondents) with organizational trust in the high category and 65.5% (167 respondents) with organizational trust in the low category.

Table 3: Distribution of Respondents Based on Organizational Trust

Organizational Trust	n	(%)
High	88	34.5
Low	167	65.5
Total	255	100

Source: Primary Data, 2024

Based on the output of Table 4, shows that of the 255 respondents at Prof. Dr. H. M. Anwar Makkatutu Bantaeng Hospital, there are 43.5% (111 respondents) with organizational justice in the high category and 56.5% (144 respondents) with organizational justice in the low category.

Table 4: Distribution of Respondents Based on Organizational Justice

Organizational Justice	n	(%)
High	111	43.5
Low	144	56.5
Total	255	100

Source: Primary Data, 2024

Based on the output of Table 5, it shows that the organizational trust variable has a significant value of $0.001 < 0.05$, which means that the organizational trust variable has a significant effect on OCB. The organizational justice variable has a significant value of $0.001 < 0.05$, which means that the organizational justice variable has a significant effect on OCB. The regression coefficient of the organizational trust variable is 1.798 (positive value), which means that an increase in organizational trust will allow OCB to occur, as well as the regression coefficient of the organizational justice variable, which is 3.974 (positive value), which means that an increase in organizational justice will allow OCB. To determine the magnitude of the influence of each influential variable, it can be seen in the Exp(B) value, or exponent value. Based on the Exp(B) value, organizational trust will have an influence of 6.035 times on OCB. Organizational justice will have an influence of 53.205 times on OCB. Based on the magnitude of the influence of independent variables on the dependent variable, the

variable that has the most influence on OCB is the organizational justice variable, which is 53.205 times.

Table 5: Logistic Regression Coefficient Test Results for Effects of Organizational Trust and Organizational Justice on Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB)

Variabel	B	df	Sig.	Exp(B)
Organizational Trust → OCB	1.798	1	0.001	6.035
Organizational Justice → OCB	3.974	1	0.001	53.205

Source: Primary Data, 2024

DISCUSSION

Based on the results of research conducted on employees at Prof. Dr. H. M. Anwar Makkatutu Bantaeng Hospital, in the univariate results show organizational trust at Prof. Dr. H. M. Anwar Makkatutu Bantaeng Hospital is in the low category, with a percentage of 65.5% (167 respondents). The low organizational trust is due to the low trust that arises between employees towards coworkers, their organization, and managers and supervisors. This can occur, possibly due to the lack of communication that is established, so that employees feel distrustful of their organization. Then they will feel no need to contribute and have no debt to their organization to pay it with OCB that is beneficial to the organization.

And multivariate results show that organizational trust has a significant positive effect on OCB, with a p-value of 0.001 <0.05, Exp(B) 6.035 times, B 1.798. This shows that the higher the organizational trust felt by employees in the hospital, the higher the level of OCB owned by employees. This is due to the fact that an organization's ability to survive depends on the presence of workers or employees who respect the organization, who act independently within it, who choose to stay inside it, and who freely work toward its goals. This study supports other studies that found a strong correlation between organizational trust and OCB [16]; [9]; [17]; [18]; [19]. Organizational trust is very important in all relationships formed in an organization. Trust has strong motivational effects that create and release positive energy, which provides collectivity [20]. However, trust can be lost quickly by a particular single behavior, although it is built in small steps over time [21]. When staff trust in their coworkers, managers, and the organization, they show more cooperative, supportive, and tolerant performance and exhibit OCB that achieves their goals effectively and efficiently.

The univariate results of organizational justice are also in the low category, which has a percentage of 56.5% (144 respondents). Low organizational justice is likely caused by the low involvement felt by employees in decision-making and the rights they receive from the organization. This is why when they feel unfairly treated, they feel no obligation to retaliate by engaging in extra-role behavior for the organization's progress.

Multivariate results show that Organizational justice has a significant positive effect on OCB, with a p-value of 0.001 <0.05, Exp(B) 53.205 times, B 3.974. This shows that the higher the organizational justice felt by employees in the hospital, the higher the level of OCB owned by employees. Employees' work attitudes and behaviors depend on the perceived fairness of the organizational outcomes they receive from their

organization. As for research that is in line with this research [22]; [23]; [24]. For many years, researchers, executives, and scientists in the domains of organizational behavior, industrial and organizational psychology, and human resources management have been deeply troubled by the problem of organizational justice. It attracted attention and demonstrates how members of their organizations feel about justice and fairness. Organizational justice impacts the organization when employees perceive unfair treatment in the workplace, and the result is negative emotions and behaviors [25]. Unfair or unjust treatment not only decreases performance but also decreases the quality of work and the level of cooperation among workers [26].

CONCLUSION

Based on the research results, it can be seen that organizational trust and organizational justice variables have a major influence on organizational citizenship behavior (OCB). Thus, in order to improve hospital performance, hospital management must focus on these two organizational continuity-related factors. This study highlights the need for paradigm shifts in hospital administration that are focused on improving attitudes and professionalism, as well as the practical implications for management and staff in hospitals. In order to improve employee performance through greater OCB, hospital staff and management must make positive adjustments toward organizational justice and organizational trust. Research can be conducted in the future with the inclusion of a more diverse population from various hospitals, including both public and private hospitals and other variables that also affect OCB, such as individual characteristic factors, work characteristic factors, leadership characteristic factors, and others, can be related to the two variables in this study.

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